

Fall Incidences Affecting Patient Safety in a MultiSpeciality Hospital-A Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Patient fall in the hospital care setting are recognized as a serious health problem since they are common and may result in injuries and complications which prolongs hospitalization, decreases patient's functional capacities and leads to increased health care costs. The safety of patients hospitalized in health services is one of the priority concerns in quality control systems. The fall suffered by the patient during their hospitalization are one of the most important occurrences in the breakdown of security and are often responsible for an increased number of hospital days and worse recovery conditions.

Objective of the Study:

1. To determine the fall risk related activity patterns in patient during hospitalization.
2. To identify and describe the incidences of fall and circumstances offall and fall related injury.
3. To evaluate the cost and outcome related to fall incidences.

Research Methodology: The study conducted is of descriptive research design. Retrospective data is collected from a tertiary hospital at Mangalore. The present study is a time bound study where the sample was selected during the one year period from May 2017 to April 2018, where the total inpatients were 15,561 out of which reported fall incidences were 25.

Results:

- The fall incidences are more in male gender and the age group between 61 to 80 years.
- The fall risk related activity is washroom fall and fall while ambulation from the bed is the highest.
- The circumstances of fall are more in disease condition and than related to medication.
- The patient outcome differs as it depends on their fall related injury.
- The length of stay also increases the patient cost. The 64% of the patient spent between 5002 rupees to 25000 rupees compared to 45001 rupees to 65000 rupees 24%.

Conclusion:

- Fall in older person and their consequences are a major global public health issue.
- The incidence rate of fall and fall injuries increases with advancing age. Fall and related injuries of hospitalized patients have a tremendous impact on health and healthcare costs. These falls and subsequent injuries have a tremendous impact on the patient, as well as directly affecting hospitals length of stay and cost per case.

Keywords: Cost, Fall, Hospitalization, Incidence, Patient outcome

INTRODUCTION

Patient fall are the second leading explanation for accidental or unintentional injury deaths worldwide. Currently, around the world, hospitals invest a considerable amount of effort into preventing patients fall during hospitalization. Fall occur commonly in older individuals and are a major health concern.

A fall consistent with WHO is defined as "an event which ends up during a person coming to rest inadvertently on the bottom or floor or other lower level" and is a frequent, preventable and dear problem that happens in hospitals worldwide.

Fall-related injuries could also be fatal or non-fatal though most are non-fatal. Falls that occur in hospitalized patients are a widespread and high threat to patient safety. Fall prevention involves managing a patient's underlying fall risk factors and optimizing the hospital's physical design and environment. There has been an increase in the number of patient falls in hospitals and other health care facilities. These still occur most often near the bedside or within the bathroom, among mentally confused or physically impaired patients.

Falls leading to injury are a prevalent patient safety problem. Elderly and frail patients with fall risk factors aren't the sole ones who are susceptible to falling in health care facilities. Any tolerant any age or ability are often in danger for a fall thanks to physiological changes thanks to a medical condition, medications, surgery, procedures, or diagnostic testing that can leave them weakened or confused. The cost of falls is dear and contributes to increasing health care expenditures.

An injurious fall can have significant personal and economic consequences for the individual and their family. As well as the injury, associated pain and disability suffered, falls can also result in fear of falling, decreased levels of activity, loss of independence, raised levels of anxiety and depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, admission to residential care and sometimes death.

There are significant costs related to falls, including patient care costs, increased length of stay.

Falls can have serious consequences for older people, their families and careers. They can cause reduced quality of life, disability, reduced physical activity, social isolation, functional decline and even death. Falls, especially recurrent falls, within the elderly are avoidable. A lack of awareness of the syndrome, risk factors and consequences of falls for older persons involve intervention, as they impact not only a private and her/his family but also society through associated direct and indirect costs. Studies in developed countries show that falls prevention programs are especially effective when targeted at individuals at increased risk of falls: persons age 75 and over and persons with a prior history of falls.

Falls are a public health problem worldwide. Hospitalization increases fall risk due to the unfamiliar environment, illnesses, and coverings. Patient falls and fall-related injuries are devastating to patients, clinicians, and therefore the health care system. The rate, intensity and price of falls identify them as a national safety and quality issue. An increase in falling as people age is associated with decreased muscle tone, strength and fitness as a result of physical inactivity. Certain medications can contribute to an increased risk of falling.

Screening may be a process that primarily aims to spot people at increased risk. In the hospital setting, a falls risk screen can be used to identify patients who require a high level of supervision and more detailed falls risk assessment.

Falls risk assessments aim to identify factors that increase falls risk, and that may be amenable to intervention. Falls risk screening may be a brief process of estimating a person's risk of falling, classifying people as being at either low risk or increased risk. Falls risk screening usually involves reviewing only a couple of items. Although it's not designed as a comprehensive assessment, positive screening on certain screen items also can provide information about intervention strategies. The purpose of screening is to spot those patients with increased falls risk who got to have increased supervision or an in depth falls risk assessment. Falls risk assessment may be a more detailed process than screening and is employed to spot underlying risk factors for falling. Some falls risk assessments also classify people into low and high falls risk groups.

Hospital staff must take all falls seriously, because falls could also be the primary and main indication of another underlying and treatable problem during a patient. Estimates of the cost of injuries and other conditions are necessary to guide decision makers in determining funding priorities and to support cost-effectiveness and cost-benefit analyses of the most effective means of preventing falls and reducing fall-related injury.

The present study aims to determine the fall risk related activity patterns, to identify and describe the incidence of falls and circumstances of falls and fall related injury and to evaluate the effect of fall related to patient cost and outcome of incident fall in patients during acute hospitalization.

RESULTS

The main activity identified during fall incidence is washroom fall and fall while ambulation from the bed is the highest compared to fall while walking, fall from trolley and fall while ambulation from the wheelchair. The patient had fall incidences more because of disease condition compared to medication side effects, and some patients side rails were down, the floor was slippery, and least is absent of foot end panel, environmental problem.

The major fall incidences is due to *disease condition* is mainly because of weakness, giddiness and convulsion, diabetic patients with hypoglycemia, Alcoholic patient with restlessness, and postoperative patient fallen in washroom and while getting from bed. Second is *Medication*, is mainly because some patients were on psychotic, analgesic medicines. Third is *Side rails were down* due to patient had fallen from sleep. In this patient they self-kept side rails down and in some staff nurses forgot to keep side rails up. Fourth is *Slippery floor* it is in the washroom while taking bath and presence of water outside the washroom. Absent of *foot end panel* it is in the orthopedic cases were foot end panel was removed to put traction, patient were trying to get up from footend when there is no traction and had fall incidence, and the final is the *Environmental* problem in which patient foot was hit to the foot step which is kept near the bedside.

The length of stay in the hospital has been increased because of patient fall in the hospital. Patients suffered with no injury have only kept for observation in wards and got discharged within three days of fall incidence. In minor injury, patients got cut over the forehead, injury in hand and leg, for them wound dressing, and suturing has been done and they got discharged within four to seven days of fall incidence. Patient suffered with laceration and bruises dressing has been done and discharged within three

DATA ANALYSIS

Figure 1 Showing Gender distribution

The above figure shows that the fall incidence is more among male (60%) than the female (40%).

Table 1: Distribution according to the age group

Age Group	Number of fall Patients
20 – 40yrs	2
41 – 60yrs	9
61 – 80yrs	11
81 – 100yrs	3
Total	25

Figure 2 Showing Age group distributions

The above figure shows that a age group between 61 to 80years is a highest fall incidences that is 44% and the age group between 41 to 60years shows 36% following age group between 81 to 100years is 12% and least is 20 to 40years is 8% .

Figure 3 Showing Month wise fall incidences

The above figure shows the month wise fall incidences in one year from May2017 to April 2018. In the month of June 2017fall incidences were 4 and in July 2017, September 2017, April 2018 fall incidences 3, and 2 in the month of May 2017, August 2017, October 2017, November 2017 and one fall incidences in December 2017, January 2018, February 2018, March 2018.

Table 2: Distribution of activity during fall incidences according to the number of fallPatients

Activity during fall incidence	Number fall patients
Washroom fall	10
Fall from bed	10
While walking fall	3
Fall from trolley	1
Fall from chair	1
Total	25

Figure 4 showing fall risk related activity patterns

The above figure shows that the more fall incidences observed in washroom and while ambulation from the bed is 40% and 12% fall while walking following 4% fall from trolley and while ambulation from wheel chair.

Table 3: Distribution according to the circumstances of fall

Circumstances of fall	Number of patients
Disease condition	13
Medication	4
Side rails were down	3
Slippery floor	3
Absent of foot end panel	1
Environmental	1
Total	25

Figure 5 Showing Circumstances of fall

The above figure shows the circumstances of fall in percentage. 52% of fall incidences occurred because of disease condition, 16% of medication and 12% of slippery floor; side rails were down following 4% of absent of foot end panel and environmental problem.

Table 4: Distribution of the patient according to the type of injury

Type of injury	Number of patients
No injury	9
Minor injury	7
Major injury	3
Fracture	3
Laceration	2
Bruises	1
Total	25

Figure 6 Showing the Type of injury

The above figure shows the 36% of patients suffered with no injury, 28% suffered with minor injury, 12% of patients ended up with major injury and fracture, 8% suffered with laceration and 4% bruises.

Table 5: Distribution according to the increase in the length of stay after the fall

Number of days	Length of stay of patient after fall
0 – 3days	11
4 – 7days	5
8 – 11days	4
12 – 15days	5
Total	25

Figure 7 showing increase in the length of stay after the fall

The above figure shows the 44% length of stay between 0 to 3 days, 20% 4 to 7 days and 16% 8 to 11 days and least is 20% between 12 to 15 days.

Figure 8 showing per patient cost

The above figure shows the patient total cost from the date of admission to fall incidences and from fall incidences to discharge of the patient.

Table 6: Distribution according to the fall incidence cost of the patient

Patient fall incidence cost in rupees	Number of patient
Less than 5000	2
5001 – 25000	16
25001 – 45000	1
45001 - 65000	6
Total	25

Figure 9 showing fall incidence cost of the patient

The above figure shows the patient fall incidence expenditure, the 64% is between 5001 rupees to 25000 rupees and 24% is between 45001 rupees to 65000 rupees and 8% is less than 5000 rupees and least is 4% between 25001 rupees to 45000 rupees.

DISCUSSION

Teasell R, McRae M and Foley N et al directed an investigation on "The rate and outcomes of falls in stroke patients during inpatient recovery: Factors identified with high danger". Destinations of the investigation are to work out the rate of falls on a stroke restoration unit; to survey the recurrence and nature of wounds; and to spot hazard factors prescient of falls, utilitarian results, and debilitations. Review associate investigation done on 238 patients, 88 (37%) encountered at least 1 fall, and practically a large portion of these (45 patients [19%]) encountered at least 2 falls. An aggregate of 180 falls were accounted for over the 5-year time frame. Of the 180 revealed falls, 33% happened when patients were utilizing their wheelchairs. Wounds happened in 22% of the detailed falls. These comprised of injuries (49%) and scraped spots (41%), principally of the upper (30.8%) and lower (25.6%) limits. Just 1 break was accounted for. Fallers would in general have lower confirmation BBS scores (half of patients with a score 30, $P < .01$) and a lower score on the affirmation arm, leg, and foot parts of the CM ($P < .05$). Patients who fell were additionally bound to be apraxic ($P < .014$) and experience the ill effects of intellectual shortfalls ($P < .01$). Rehash fallers had lower confirmation FIM scores ($P < .01$) when contrasted and non-fallers. Finish of the examination is; in spite of the fact that patients going through stroke restoration encountered countless falls, the rate of genuine injury was little. Patients who experienced at any rate 1 fall had essentially lower BBS, FIM, and CM arm, leg, and foot scores contrasted and non-fallers. These information propose that gatherings of stroke patients who are in danger for falls inside the recovery setting can be distinguished by utilizing an assortment of hindrance and utilitarian appraisals. This data might be conceivably

valuable for planning mediations coordinated at decreasing fall recurrence among stroke survivors. ^[1]

Schwendimann Rene, Buhler Hugo, Geest De Sabina et al led an investigation on "Falls and ensuing wounds in hospitalized patients: impacts of an interdisciplinary falls anticipation program". Observational investigation was done on a sequential overview plan and was directed from January first in 1999 to December 31st in 2003 of every a metropolitan public showing emergency clinic in the City of Zurich in Switzerland. The populace under examination included grown-up patients, hospitalized in the branches of inside medication, geriatrics, and medical procedure. A sum of 34,972 hospitalized patients (mean age: 67.3, SD $\pm$ 19.3 years; female 53.6%, mean length of stay: 11.9 $\pm$ 13.2 days, mean nursing care time per day: 3.5 $\pm$ 1.4 Hours) were seen during the investigation time frame. By and large, a sum of 3,842 falls influenced 2,512 (7.2%) of the hospitalized patients. From these falls, 2,552 (66.4%) were without wounds, while 1,142 (29.7%) falls brought about minor wounds, and 148 (3.9%) falls brought about significant wounds. The general fall rate in the emergency clinics' patient populace was 8.9 falls per 1,000 patient days. The fall rates changed somewhat from 9.1 falls in 1999 to 8.6 falls in 2003. After the execution of the IFP, in 2001 a slight lessening to 7.8 falls per 1,000 patient days was noticed ($p = 0.086$). The yearly extent of minor and significant wounds didn't diminish after the execution of the IFP. From 1999 to 2003, patient attributes changed regarding slight builds (female sex, age, devoured nursing care time) or diminishes (length of clinic stay), just as the predominance of fall hazard factors expanded up to 46.8% in those patients who fell. Following the execution of an interdisciplinary falls anticipation program, neither the frequencies of falls nor ensuing wounds diminished significantly. Future investigations need to consolidate methodologies to augment and assess continuous adherence to intercessions in emergency clinic falls anticipation programs. ^[2]

Abreu Cidalina, Mendes Aida, Monteiro Jose et al directed investigation on "Falls in medical clinic settings: a longitudinal report". This investigation means to evaluate the predominance of falls, comprehend their outcomes, recognize causes and break down mediation systems to forestall them. This is a spellbinding longitudinal investigation, from 2007 to 2009, in which attendants recorded patients' falls in a medication ward, utilizing a scale produced for this end. Most falls happened with part of the way reliant patients, with a mean age going from 64 to 74 years. The room was, in these years, where the greater part of these falls happened. Albeit most falls didn't have outcomes, they were seen in 36% of the cases. The quantity of falls expanded over time of the investigation. There was additionally a distinction in the level of events in the early evening and night shifts (39% in 2007, 57% in 2008 and 64% in 2009). The discoveries show that exploration can be a significant asset to change attendants' practices and an additional worth in care direction, along these lines adding to expand quality. The discoveries demonstrate that examination can be a significant asset to change attendants' practices and an additional worth in care direction, along these lines adding to build quality. The utilization of hazard evaluation scales and the plan of relevantly sufficient rules will request further examination and preparing for all wellbeing professionals. ^[3]

Richardson Annette, Carter Rachel directed an investigation on "Falls in basic consideration: a neighborhood survey to distinguish frequency and hazard". Detailed falls episodes were looked into reflectively utilizing a nearby occurrence announcing framework, over a 2-year time span from four basic consideration units. 42 episodes were evaluated demonstrating a low pace of injury and low pace of event (0.99 falls/1000 bed days). The middle period of fallers was 58 years and the most well-known danger factor for falls was disarray or fomentation, trailed by patients endeavoring to assemble against guidance. Fundamentally sick patients were less inclined to fall and were bound to be more youthful than patients falling on an intense consideration ward. Neuroscience/injury fundamentally sick patients were bound to fall than general basically sick patients; this was required to be a direct result of the expanded presence of disarray or unsettling in this gathering. The nearby framework used to report falls created challenges in distinguishing hazard factors in a reliable way. Despite the fact that constraints exist, this survey has empowered the improvement of more appropriate neighborhood basic consideration falls hazard factor evaluation and intercessions to limit the danger of falling. ^[4]

Hendrich Ann, Nyhuis Alen, et al directed an examination on "Clinic falls: advancement of a prescient model for clinical practice". A review case-control study identified with falls was led at a 1,120-bed intense consideration tertiary clinic. The case (fall) test comprised of 102 falls and 236 control (non-fall) outlines during a 1month period. An instrument created by Hendrich (1988) was changed for use in the investigation. Segment information and hazard factors were recorded. Engaging insights included danger factor rates for each example and the comparing univariate relative dangers. Strategic relapse was utilized to build up a multi-variate hazard factor model with seven danger factors. The huge danger factors were ongoing history of falls, despondency, adjusted end examples, unsteadiness or vertigo, essential malignancy finding, disarray, and changed versatility. The changed relative dangers were changed over to hazard focuses to be utilized to survey a patient's degree of fall hazard. Inside the informational collection, an affectability of 77% (79 of 102) and explicitness of 72% (169 of 236) were determined. The model was cross-approved in a 1987 informational collection with an affectability of 83% (59 of 71) and explicitness of 66% (106 of 161). ^[5]

Hitcho B. Eileen, Krauss J. Melissa, Birge Stanley et al led an investigation on "Qualities and Circumstances of Falls in a Hospital Setting". A Prospective illustrative investigation of inpatient's falls led. A sum of 183 patients fell during the investigation time frame. The normal time of patients who fell was 63.4 years (range 17 to 96). Numerous falls were unassisted (79%) and happened in the patient's room (85%), during the evening/short-term (59%), and during

ambulation (19%). A big part of the falls (half) were end related, which was more normal in patients more than 65 years of age (83% versus 48%; $P < .001$). Disposal related falls expanded the danger of fall-related injury (changed chances proportion, 2.4; 95% certainty span 1.1 to 5.3). The medication and nervous system science administrations had the most elevated fall rates (both were 6.12 falls per 1,000 patient-days), and the most noteworthy patient to nurture proportions (6.5 and 5.3, respectively). Falls in the emergency clinic influence youthful just as more seasoned patients, and include end related exercises. Further examinations are important to forestall medical clinic falls and lessen fall injury rates. [6]

Wong A. Catherine, Recktenwald J. Angela, Jones L. Marilyn et al directed an examination on "The Cost of Serious Fall-Related Injuries at Three Midwestern Hospitals". A review case-control study directed in 57 emergency clinic inpatients released between January 1, 2004, and October 16, 2006, who supported a genuine fall-related injury (crack, subdural hematoma, any injury bringing about careful intercession, or demise) were recognized through the episode announcing framework and coordinated to nonfaller inpatient controls by clinic, age inside five years, year of release, and conclusion related gathering (DRG). The aftereffect of the investigation is multivariate examinations shown that operational expenses for fallers with genuine injury, as contrasted and controls, were \$13,316 more ($p < .01$; 95% certainty span [CI], \$1,395–\$35,561) and that fallers remained 6.3 days longer than nonfallers ($p < .001$; 95% CI, 2.4–14.9). Univariate examinations showed they were additionally altogether bound to have diabetes with organ harm, moderate to serious renal illness, and a higher mean score on the Charlson Comorbidity Index. Fallers with genuine injury cost \$13,806 more ($p < .001$; 95% CI, \$5,808–\$29,450) and remained 6.9 days longer ($p < .001$; 95% CI, 2.8–14.9). Conclusion of the examination is in-patients who supported a genuine fall-related injury had higher all out operational expenses and longer lengths of stay than nonfallers. Notwithstanding potential restrictions with respect to the expense distribution techniques, the investigation included information from three distinct emergency clinics, and supplemental multivariate examinations adapting to scholarly clinic status didn't seriously influence the results. [7]

INTERPRETATION

The statistical derivations of the study when compared with the various previous scholarly studies, the following points are observed in the current study:

- The main reason for the fall incidences is disease condition, medication, side rails not in position, slippery floor, foot end panel missing and environmental problems.
- Fall risk related activity is washroom fall, fall while ambulation from the bed, fall while walking, fall from trolley and fall while ambulation from the wheelchair.
- The type of injury related fall incidences is 9 patients suffered with no injury, 7 patients suffered with minor injury, 3 patients ended up with major injury and fracture and 2 patients suffered with laceration and one patient with bruises from the study sample.
- Patient attitude to not to disturb their relative from sleep and also being independent without calling staff nurses for help, so most of the fall incidences happen at night and patient is injured. Depending upon the type of injury patient length of stay also increased and also patient expenditures. 64% patient spent highest expenditure after the fall incidence.

SUGGESTIONS

In the health care setting, fall related injuries are wider adverse effect on the various type of patients from fall injuries. It increasing the morbidity, mortality rate and also increasing the cost of the treatment. Successful strategies include the utilization of a uniform assessment tool to spot fall and injury risk factors, assessing a private patient's risks. This will reduce by identifying patients who at highest risk for sustaining serious injury from a fall, multifactorial assessment and systematic reporting of falls incidents and their effect.

1. Lead an effort to raise awareness of the need to prevent falls resulting in injury: Communicate safety information to clinical and non-clinical staff at every level.
2. Establish an interdisciplinary falls injury prevention team or evaluate the membership of the team in place: to assure organizational infrastructure and capacity to reduce injury risk from falls. Reducing falls resulting in injury is everyone's responsibility. Include nursing, physicians, environmental services, information technology, pharmacy, physical and occupational therapy, quality and risk management.
3. A standardized hand-off communication process for communicating patient risk for falls with injury between caregivers that includes identifying specific areas of risk and patient-specific interventions to mitigate the risk. Using white boards to speak fall risks to staff on all shifts; incorporating alerts, tasks, records and prompts into the electronic medical record; or initiating a bedside shift report with the patient that includes fall risk concerns.
4. Cognition/Delirium mental status – screen and assess and plan care.
5. Mobility – assess and mobilising plan: Balance and mobility are often poorer when a person is in hospital.
6. Toileting – assess and toileting plan: increase nursing rounds.

7. Medications – review and monitor use of: antipsychotics, antidepressants, sedatives/hypnotics, or opioids and proper supervising the patients who have received sedation or general anaesthesia Educating families.
8. Address risk of serious injury – monitor high risk fall patients on anticoagulants. Where identified, ensure osteoporotic and Vitamin D for frail older patients is instigated.
9. Provide and Maintaining the healthy and safe hospital environment for all type patients, including paediatric and geriatric
10. Appropriate nursing care to all the patients. Such as educate the patient and their families, Assist the patients with ambulation, maintaining the very clean floors and the toilets. Necessary items should be keeping near to the patient.
11. Daily assessing the patient condition changes till until the patient gets discharge safely and when patient needs shift from one department to another department.
12. Follow the standard safety measures for all type of patients for preventing the fall related injuries and at their risk.
13. Proper implementation of the incident reporting system for immediate risk assessment and for improvement of the fall prevention strategy.
14. Constructing the well engineer planned health care set-up for easy reach out to the patient which is necessary for daily fulfilment of patients as well as medical staffs.

CONCLUSION

The in-clinic falls is a worldwide wonder that represents numerous inconveniences for patients whose wellbeing has effectively been undermined upon confirmation. The vast majority of the falls are expected and accordingly preventable, and fruitful standard anticipation methods include basic factor assessment, with the utilization of appraisal scales for the assurance of high fall hazard patients. The aftereffects of the accepted procedures highlight the way that the disposal of ecological elements, the arrangement of assistive gadgets, the audit of the patient's prescription, the legitimate correspondence between the medical services groups and family just as the steady survey of post-fall investigations in blend with the evaluation of variables identifying with explicit establishments can prompt critical decrease of in-clinic falls.

The medical care and nursing groups assume a most significant part in the general avoidance of falls, since they are the people who communicate with patients the most. Subsequently, for the execution of any fruitful program, the groups should be given the legitimate preparing to perceive patients who are in danger of falling and the self-rule to carry out and evaluate the advantages of various and individualized safeguard measures with the utilization of data innovation frameworks and devices. At that point, working close by all groups answerable for the treatment of the patient also as the organization; they can achieve positive results. To accomplish this coordination, an authoritative culture and operational practices that advance cooperation and correspondence, just as individual skill are required. This is the best way to carry out a complete culture of security in a clinic and for a fundamental decrease of falls.

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